

PRODUCTION OF BIO-COAGULANT FOR APPLICATION IN TREATMENT OF WATER

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Abstract

Chemical/synthetic coagulants are widely used to remove suspended solids and organic loads from water, but they pose several environmental and public health issues due to their chronic toxicity. The effectiveness of low cost agro-based materials namely Tamarindus Indica and Moringa Oleifera seed powders produced under cryogenic condition to act as natural or biological coagulants for the treating water is presented in this study. Two water resources: “Kukkarahalli” lake water and back wash effluent water from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant were used for the study. The experimental runs were conducted using mixture of cryo treated Tamarindus Indica and Moringa Oleifera seed powders at various dosages. The laboratory investigations were carried out to determine the multiple effects of physical parameters at different dosage of mixed natural coagulant. The study evaluated the performance of these natural coagulants in terms of the percentage removal of turbidity, alkalinity, total hardness, nitrates, phosphates, total solids, BOD and plate count test for two water samples at varying coagulant dosage. The results showed the best performance (turbidity removal =97.61% and 94,21%, alkalinity removal=41,5% and 15,3%, total hardness= 33,33% and 15.3%, nitrates removal =98.4% and 96.28%, phosphates removal =33.33% and 69.5%, total solids removal =88% and 80.8%, BOD removal = 97,2% and 75% and plate count test removal=94% and 98% respectively for back wash effluent water from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples).Despite higher cost of treatment, the use of natural coagulants in water treatment provide sustainable solutions while reducing the negative impact of synthetic coagulants on the environment and public health.

Keywords: Natural Coagulant, Tamarindus Indica and Moringa Oleifera seed powder, jar test.

1.0 Introduction

Water is surely one of the main elements that are involved in the human development considering its influence on human lives. The presence or absence of impurities depends on the source of the water. For example, suspended matter is commonly found in surface water, but it would not be expected in ground water because, of the littering action of the aquifer. To evaluate whether the specific impurities are harmful, one must determine the nature and the amount of the impurities present, the uses to be made of the water, and the tolerance for various impurities for each use [1]. In addition to suspended solid, water also contains colloidal particles, which will be in continuous motion. In order to remove such fine particle from water, certain chemicals called coagulants are used [2].

Coagulation is a process for combining small particles into larger aggregates (flocs) and for adsorbing dissolved organic matter on to particulate aggregates so that these impurities can be removed in subsequent solid/liquid separation processes[3]. Turbidity and colour removal is one of the most important steps in water treatment process, which is generally achieved using coagulants. Many coagulants are widely used in conventional water treatment processes, based on their chemical characteristics. These coagulants are classified into inorganic, synthetic organic polymers, and natural coagulants. The application of natural materials for clarifying turbid waters of rivers is an ancient and home-based practice in tropical developing

countries where these natural materials act as primary coagulants[4]. Aluminium and iron coagulants are commonly used in most industries. However, when aluminium is used as a coagulant in waste water treatment, it can caused several bad effect on human health such as intestinal constipation, loss of memory, convulsions, abdominal colic's, loss of energy and learning difficulties[5].Hence nowadays, there has been great attention in the improvement and implementation of natural coagulants in wastewater treatment. These natural coagulants can be formed or extracted from animal, microorganisms and also plant. Natural coagulants used [6]. Although there are new techniques for water and wastewater treatment, however, coagulation/flocculation step is an essential process in the treatment of surface water at which includes removal of turbidity from water, the use of natural coagulants, aiming at a better quality of treated water by reducing the use of chemicals [7]. Coagulant extract from naturally available material like seeds of plant may be a good alternative to chemical coagulants. A natural coagulant will improve the quality of treated sewage and also recover plant nutrients in the form of sludge. Natural coagulants may be support to secondary treatment based on microbial activities, which has been badly affected by chemical coagulation[8]. In the present study an attempt has been made to determine the removal efficiency of different physico chemical water quality parameters by using Tamarindus Indica seed powder (monotypic genus of trees) and Moringa Oleifera seed powders (family of Moringaceae) as used a bio coagulant in water treatment.

2.0 Materials and methodology

The seed wings and coat from selected good quality Moringa Oleifera seeds were removed and the kernel was retained, for processing. The Tamarindus Indica seeds were washed with water to remove dust and pulp and the clean seeds were dried in the shade for 24 hrs. The grinding trials were done with cryogen (liquid Nitrogen), for the Moringa Oleifera and Tamarindus Indica seeds

2.1 Preparation of Moringa Oleifera and Tamarindus Indica seed powder suspension

5 grams of Moringa Oleifera and Tamarindus Indica seed powder was put in a high-speed mixer and 200 ml of distilled water was added and blended for 30 seconds in a magnetic stirrer. The resulting suspension was filtered through a filter paper (Whatmann filter paper, No.44) and the filtrate is made up to 500 ml to give a stock solution of approximate 1000mg/L. Jar test experiments is conducted for evaluating and optimizing the coagulation – flocculation process.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research works were carried out to find physico chemical parameters removal efficiency of the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples by using the mixture of cryo treated Moringa Oleifera and Tamarindus Indica seeds powder at 1:1 ratio as a bio coagulant by varying coagulants dosage to find the optimum dosage.

3.1 Turbidity

The primary goal of coagulation – flocculation is turbidity removal. The maximum amount of 97.61% and 94.21% of turbidity is removed at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 1

Figure 1: % removal of turbidity with varying dosage in mg/L

Also at optimum dosage, there is a decreased residual turbidity, increased removals with increased initial turbidity after the period of settling period. This observation may be attributed to increased suspended particles available for adsorption and inter-particle bridge formation, effecting in an increased particle collision frequency and agglomeration rate.[9]

3.2 Alkalinity

Figure 2: % removal of Alkalinity with varying dosage in mg/L

The maximum amount of 41.5 % and 15.3 % of alkalinity is removed at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 2

The slight decrease in alkalinity of all water samples may be due to precipitation of insoluble products of the reaction between the coagulant (Mixture of cryo treated Moringa Oleifera and Tamarindus Indica seed powders) and the hardness causing ions.

3.3 Total hardness

The maximum amount of 33.33 % and 15.2 % of total hardness is removed at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 3

Figure 3: % removal of total hardness with varying dosage in mg/L

3.4 Nitrates

The maximum removal efficiency of nitrate ions in the treated water were 98.40 % and 96.28% at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 4

Figure 4: % removal of nitrates with varying dosage in mg/L

3.5 Phosphates

The maximum removal efficiency of phosphate ions in the treated water were 33.40 % and 69.5% at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 5

Figure 5: % removal of phosphates with varying dosage in mg/L

The phosphates are not directly involved in the coagulation reaction because of its soluble nature and therefore a significant fraction remains in the treated water. Small quantity of phosphorous is essential for biological life but in excess promotes the growth of algae.

3.6 Total solids

The amount of total solids present in the samples goes on decreasing with increase dosage and reach maximum 88.1 % and 80.8% at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l and 150 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: % removal of total solids with varying dosage in mg/L

3.7 BOD

The Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), which is a measure of oxygen utilized by microorganisms during biological oxidation of organic matter contained in the liquid waste.

The amount of BOD present in the samples goes on decreasing with increase dosage and reach maximum 97.2 % and 75 % at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l and 150 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 7

Figure 7: % removal of BOD with varying dosage in mg/L

3.8 Plate count

The amount of plate count present in the samples goes on decreasing with increase dosage and reach maximum 94 % and 98 % at an coagulant dosage of 100 mg/l and 200 mg/l for the back wash effluent from “Vani Vilas” water treatment plant and “Kukkarahalli” lake water samples respectively and results are tabulated in the Figure 8

Figure 8: % removal of plate count with varying dosage in mg/L

Scanning Electronic Microscope (SEM) has been a primary tool for characterizing the surface morphology and fundamental physical properties of the coagulant. The prepared coagulant samples were analyzed by scanning electron microscope before using as coagulant for treating water samples. It was observed that both coagulants prepared, more and more pores were exposed, and it was predicted that these pores would have positive effect on coagulation. The coagulation processes of both prepared coagulants by adding liquid Nitrogen(cryogen) leads to corrosion of the surface of carbonaceous material and introduce micro, macro and meso pores, which increase the porosity volume and connects the pores. The Scanning Electronic Microscope image of cryo Tamarindus Indica and Moringa Oleifera seed powders were presented in Plate 1 and 2, which gives an idea of morphological study of both bio coagulants.

Plate 1: Micrograph of cryo grounded “Moringa Oleifera” seed powder

Plate 2: Micrograph of cryo grounded “Tamarindus Indica” seed powder

4.0 Conclusion:

The inorganic synthetic coagulants, particularly alum, has been widely used in water treatment for turbidity removal due to high efficiency and low cost; however, usage of these chemical compounds poses several environmental and public health issues due to their chronic toxicity. The natural biological coagulants – the mixture of cryo treated *Moringa Oleifera* and *Tamarindus Indica* seeds powder at 1:1 ratio used in this study, have exhibited comparable performance in removing turbidity and other water quality parameters like alkalinity, total hardness, nitrates, phosphates, total solids, BOD and plate count test for two different water samples at varying coagulant dosage. The most importantly, the natural coagulants are non-hazardous to the environment and public health. So, there is an urgent need to replace these chemical coagulants by natural coagulants to achieve environmentally sustainable treatment of water.

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